

institution with non-governmental and non-commercial organizations (NG and NCOs) working in Uzbekistan.

At the process of above mentioned events, the most important democratic trends of forming and dividing the financial means source and national system which can serve as international standards is important because of supporting independent system of “the third sector”. At the same time, we try to give a brief explanation about non-governmental organizations, their essence and the history of the origin.

A *non-governmental organization (NGO)* is a not-for-profit organization, which does not serve to get revenue pursue social effects and operate independently from the states and other international organizations. They are usually provided with financial resources through donations but some avoid formal funding altogether and are run primarily by volunteers. NGOs are highly diverse groups of organizations engaged in a wide range of activities, and take different forms in different parts of the world. Some may have charitable status, while others may be registered for tax exemption based on recognition of social purposes. Others may be fronts for political, religious, or other interests.

The number of NGOs worldwide is estimated about 3.7 million (1). In Russia, there are 277,000 NGOs (2). In India, it is estimated to have had around 2 million NGOs in 2009, just over one NGO per 600 Indians, and many times the number of primary schools and the centers of primary health in India (3)]. In China it is estimated to have approximately 440,000 officially registered NGOs [1].

NGOs are difficult to define, and the term ‘NGO’ is not always used consistently. In some countries the term NGO is applied to an organization that in another country would be called an *NPO* (non-profit organization), and vice versa. There are many different classifications of NGO in use. The most common focus is on “orientation” and “level of operation”. An NGO’s orientation refers to the type of activities it takes on. These activities might include human rights, environmental, improving health, or development work. An NGO’s level of operation indicates the scale at which an organization works, such as local, regional, national, or international [2].

The term “non-governmental organization” was firstly coined in 1945, during the United Nations (UN) was created [3]. The UN, as an intergovernmental organization, made it possible approved specialized international non-state agencies — *i. e.*, non-governmental organizations — to be awarded observer status at its assemblies and some of its meetings. Later the term became used more widely all over the world. Today, according to the UN, any kind of private organization that is independent from government control can be termed an “NGO”, provided it is not-for-profit, non-prevention, and not simply an opposition political party.

In accordance with Item 2 of the law “About non-profit organizations” of Republic of Uzbekistan, *Non-profit organization* — the self-governing organization that consists of physical and (or) legal entities who are established on a voluntary basis, is not main purpose to income (profit) so well distribute income (profit) among its participants (members) (4).

Deeping and having improvements of conceptions of citizenship society plays important role for developing many other institutions of society in our country. Its effective results have been appearing according to the social partnerships of non-government and government organizations, developing of social economic improvements and implementations, solving humanitarian problems, defending benefits of every field in the life of population of country, providing liberty and rights of inhabitants.

For providing social companionship improvements money resources should be divided, and with this, increasing of having importance of social projects, supporting financial resources, monitoring its results the main duties should be carried out. Below there is given quantity growth of non-government organizations dynamics during 5 years (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Dynamics of the growth of NGOs quantity in Uzbekistan (5).

The Figure 1 shows, NGOs quantity increased is about 1.6 times in 2014 than 2009, where, 1.5 times than 2011.

Now we'll look through financial resources of statistics points of these organizations (Figure 2). Figure 2 shows that financial growth had been increased about 2.7 times during 7 years.

Figure 2. Dynamics of financial quantity growth of government money means (billion) (5).

There is not only government budget but also another government grants, subsidies also are up. It can be shown according to this information below (Figure 3).

Figure 3. In 2008–2013 years NGOs and citizenship society’s institutions finances whole quantity (5).

For having basic ways of monitoring of social partnerships we have to follow given below:

– Organizing distribution of supporting NGOs finance and reserves, deepening proposals of another institutions and NGOs, citizenship society, solving socio-economic problems of districts, reception, social and main important circles and projects for social working of inhabitants, making main, basic financial programs of them;

– Providing transparency of financial distributions, developing of NGOs and other institutions of citizenship society, improving their working, effectiveness also, attracting community and public works attention for these providing democratic customs, human rights and liberty with debating problems;

– Using funds with the main aims and purposes, monitoring the control of working NGOs and their projects, programs for financial independent of inhabitants society;

– Promoting to deepen cooperation with the local authorities and NGOs in the implementation of programs and projects and the most important priority programs and projects in society, and the process of strengthening the role of NGOs and other civil society institutions in the democratization of social life;

– The development of recommendations to improve the economic and legal guarantees in providing for the development of free and independent regulatory framework of NGOs and other civil society institutions;

Other tasks that do not contradict the legislation.

It has maintained its relevance to improve the authorization of the report presented result of working with the media and intellectual development which is wide coverage in the media in the process of implementation of projects of social importance. Now, the contents of the income collected by NGO activity, consider the following graph (Figure 4).

There is scientific base and interdisciplinary subject in the formation and accumulation of NGOs income. The world of scientific literature that “*fundraising*” is to be interpreted English

translation (fund— money, finance, raise— address, collection) collection of funds or the address of financing.

Figure 4. The classification of NGOs formed income through their business activity [4].

Fundraising: is a part of a development strategy of non-governmental organizations (NGOs), is an implement of providing social interaction with government agencies and businesses and the preparation of projects for donor agencies and their sales. To create a favorable fiscal–financial and legal framework for effective social cooperation it’s required analysis of the national legal system of the provision of logistical, technical and financial in NGOs’ economic stability and changes them.

In conclusion, we can say that the non-profit sector, and their financial resources and the fulfillment of the social project of this “third sector” monitoring is important. In this way, it’s based on their revenue collection strategy for future projects service.

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